

AQUASERV Data Management Plan 42171

Version 2

Description

This project, integrated into a mesocosm experiment at the ECIMAT facility (Ría de Vigo), investigates the cumulative impacts of Ocean Alkalinity Enhancement (OAE) and ocean warming on planktonic communities. More specifically, the main aim of this specific project is to determine the individual and interactive effects of elevated temperature and OAE on the zooplankton community structure and trophic function within a productive coastal ecosystem. This project will assess the impact of the observed zooplankton responses on the planktonic food web functioning by analyzing changes in the abundance of top planktonic predators and linking zooplankton dynamics to host-measured metrics of Net Community Production (NCP) and phytoplankton biomass. It will also quantify the individual effects of elevated temperature and elevated alkalinity on zooplankton abundance and community composition in the Ría de Vigo plankton assemblage. And finally, we will determine the potential interactive effects (synergy or antagonism) of the combined temperature and alkalinity stress on key zooplankton functional groups (e.g., copepods, meroplankton) and their overall abundance. The project will generate zooplankton taxonomic and abundance data as well as statistical analysis to determine the effects of the treatments.

These data will be processed to support peer-reviewed publications and will be archived in compliance with FAIR principles.

Funder

Grant

Researchers

Justine Courboules (0000-0002-7826-5063)

Organizations

1. Main Information

Title of Plan: [AQUASERV Data Management Plan 42171](#)

Project title: [Warming and Alkalinity Impacts on Zooplankton communities](#)

Home Institution: [Justine Courboulès Cplankton micro-company](#)

Hosting Institution: [Universidade de Vigo](#)

Date of TNA: [13_06_2026 to 01_07_2026](#)

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[Justine Courboules \(0000-0002-7826-5063\)](#)

Contact: [Courboules Justine \(justine.courboules@hotmail.fr\)](mailto:Courboules Justine (justine.courboules@hotmail.fr))

Access: [Public](#)

2. Ethics

Introduction:

Not applicable. The project involves only natural plankton communities (non-vertebrate organisms) and is conducted strictly within enclosed, controlled mesocosm bags at the ECIMAT facility. There is no manipulation of vertebrates, no access to personal human data, and no release of modified components into the open marine environment needing a specific ethic declaration.

3. Dataset descriptions

Introduction:

Descriptions

[AQUASERV project: Warming and Alcalinity Impacts on Zooplankton communities](#)

This description covers the datasets generated for the Zooplankton part of the mesocosm experiment conducted at ECIMAT (Ría de Vigo).

Template: [AQUASERV | generic | template](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Types of data and usage

1.1.1 Data Types

I will be counting and identifying zooplankton organisms using a binocular and reporting counts and identification in a spreadsheet (CSV)

I will be analyzing the abundance dynamics and individual or synergistic effects of the treatments with R scripts (.R)

1.1.2 Data Creation

The data will be the result of the zooplankton samples collected from the mesocosms and identified and counted and analyzed.

1.1.3 Published Data Re-use

No

1.1.4 Data size

Less than 4 GBs.

2 FAIR Data Publication

2.1 Findable

2.1.1 Data Publication Repository

The final processed ecological datasets (zooplankton taxonomic identification and abundance counts) and statistical scripts will be published in SEANOE and receive a permanent Digital Object Identifier (DOI) for citation and tracking.

Data Format: Zooplankton taxa abundance matrices will be uploaded as long-term interoperable tabular formats (.csv) and Statistical analysis will be uploaded as R scripts (.R)

Metadata: Detailed information concerning the experimental design, sampling and analysis methods will be provided on the dataset page on seanoe; openly available and directly linked to the dataset files. This information is the equivalent of a readme file that explains what, when, where, by whom, and how the data were collected; it will be openly available on the homepage of the dataset in SEANOE.

2.1.2 Metadata collection

Who, When and Where?

I will collect the following information in a spreadsheet: the names and ORCID IDs of all the people involved in the work, the name of the experimental facility, the dates of the sample collection and the subsequent sample and data processing.

What?

I will note and ask the TA service provider for the brand of the sampling material and the binocular used for the counting.

Identification of the zooplankton organisms will be done in agreement with the WoRMS taxonomic names.

How?

The protocols used for sampling and analysing the zooplankton organisms will be fully described in the main page of the dataset on Seanoë.

All the information described above will be detailed in the dataset specific page on Seanoë directly linked to the datasets files. This text will be the equivalent of a readme file describing fully the metadata of the datasets and scripts.

2.2 Accessible

2.2.1 Repository

2.2.1.1 Open Access Data Repositories

Yes

Yes. SEANOë (Sea Innovation and Data Network) is a fully Open Access repository. All uploaded datasets (zooplankton taxonomic abundance matrices) and their associated metadata will be publicly visible, searchable, and freely downloadable to anyone without any access restrictions or registration walls, in full alignment with EU open science mandates.

2.2.1.2 Persistent URLs and identifiers

Yes

2.2.2 Research Data

2.2.2.1 Licence

CC-BY 4.0.

2.2.2.2 Data Publication Embargo

No

No

2.2.2.3 Restricted Data Usage

No

No

2.2.2.4 Unpublished Data

No

No

2.3 Interoperable

2.3.1 Open Data Formats

Yes

Yes

2.3.2 Vocabularies and Ontologies

I will use WoRMS (World Register of Marine Species) standard for all zooplankton taxonomic identifications (ranging from phylum/class to genus levels, depending on the specimen preservation and resolution).

2.4 Re-useable (and reproducible)

2.4.1 Methods and Protocols

Yes

The protocols and methods used to produce the dataset will be described in detail in the main page of the dataset on Seanoe along with the other metadata.

3 Other issues

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